

The Chemistry of Jute-lignin. Part VIII. Methylation of Lignin.

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Of the constituent groups that lignin contains, besides methoxyl, hydroxyl is the only group regarding the presence of which there seems to be no difference of opinion. Many investigators have carried out methylation and acetylation of lignin obtained from various sources. But the results of methylation so far available, scarcely show any concordance as regards the highest methoxyl value and the number of OH groups present in lignin, when a definite mol. wt. is assigned to it. Heuser and co-workers (*Cellulosechem.*, 1921, 2, 81) methylated HCl-lignin from pine-wood with dimethyl sulphate and 10% NaOH at 60° and obtained a final product with 26.29 % methoxyl. The original lignin had a methoxyl content of 14.65 %, which means 4 OCH₃ groups in a mol. wt. of 846 for lignin provided, of course, it lost no methoxyl in the course of isolation. Now, 26.29% of OCH₃ in the fully methylated product corresponds to a figure which is less than 8 but more than 7 methoxyl groups, assuming that 846 represents the correct mol. wt. of lignin. Urban (*Cellulosechem.*, 1926, 7, 73) employed 45 % KOH and dimethyl sulphate below 26° for the methylation of spruce-wood lignin and got a product with the highest methoxyl value (32.4%). Dimethyl sulphate and alkali under various conditions have been used by Holmberg and Wintzell (*Ber.*, 1921, 54, 2471), Powell and Whittaker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 357), Friedrich and Diwald (*Monatsh.*, 1925, 46, 44) as well as by Fuchs and Daur (*Cellulosechem.*, 1931, 12, 104) for the purpose of methylating different lignins but the results are all different.

It has been shown by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 691) that the dioxymethylene group is a common constituent of lignin and also that this group suffers partial decomposition during isolation by acid hydrolysis under usual conditions. As the percentage of OH thus appearing essentially depends on the extent to which the separated lignin loses its O-CH₂-O group, obviously the methy-

lation value can never be expected to be the same. This is actually the fact. In order to get an idea of the exact number of OH groups in lignin, therefore, one should start with the genuine lignin with all the $\text{O-CH}_2\text{-O}$ groups intact. From this point of view, it was thought worth while to study in detail the methylation of jute-lignin to see how many OH groups it actually contains.

Jute-lignin, separated in the ordinary way, was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and KOH according to Urban's method (*loc. cit.*); the highest methoxyl value that could be reached (35—36%) was not in any simple ratio with its original methoxyl content, taking as before 830 as the mol. wt. of jute-lignin. But when lignin isolated at low temperature taking the same precautions as mentioned in a previous paper (*ibid.*, 1934, 12, 691) was similarly methylated, the final methoxyl value was always 34.51%.

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 168) it was stated that on comparing the methoxyl values of raw and delignified jute, it was found that jute-lignin isolated at room temperature in the usual way suffered a loss of 1.96% of methoxyl. The lignin thus separated had 16.41% OMe whilst it should have contained 18.37% OMe, had all the methoxyls remained in it. By isolating lignin by the modified method of the author (*loc. cit.*) it has now been possible to obtain a sample of lignin with 19.18% of OMe which fact, therefore, shows its genuine character. Accepting 830 as the mol. wt. of jute-lignin, 5 methoxyl groups in the molecule means 18.66% of methoxyl; while actually 19.18% has been found. This sample had all the $\text{O-CH}_2\text{-O}$ unaffected as it yielded 2.78% of formaldehyde and was insoluble in dilute caustic alkalis. The latter fact shows that no free phenolic group was present in it; it did not reduce Fehling's solution. The figure 34.51% of methoxyl means 10 methoxyl in all, hence 5 additional OCH_3 groups have entered the molecule. Genuine jute-lignin, therefore, contains 5 OH groups.

[In a previous communication (Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 568), it has been shown that the reducing action of lignin is due to two OH groups in the *ortho*-position attached to the benzene ring, formed as a result of splitting off of formaldehyde from the dioxymethylene group in jute-lignin during isolation and not to any aldehyde group. Further evidence has now been available to corroborate this view. Jute-lignin boiled with 28% sulphuric acid under reflux for 3-4 hours reduced Fehling's solution very readily. This was methylated in the usual way repeatedly until the methoxyl value was

constant. But the methylated product no longer reduced Fehling's solution. Had the reducing action of lignin been due to an aldehyde group, this would not have been the case.

In numerous estimations of methoxyl in jute-lignin by Zeisel's method (with Perkin's modification) it has always been observed that CH_3I first appeared at $92^\circ\text{--}93^\circ$. This was also the case with vanillin and vanillic acid. This striking similarity indicates, therefore, that vanillin residue is present in lignin, which is in agreement with experimental facts. In other words, in jute-lignin OCH_3 is linked to the benzene ring, which has also been shown by Freudenberg and others (*Ber.*, 1929, 62, 1554). In the case of methylated lignin, the CH_3I appeared at $84^\circ\text{--}85^\circ$, from which fact it may be inferred that the methoxyl groups have during methylation entered not the benzene ring (as no free phenolic group was present in the original lignin) but the side-chain.

Genuine jute-lignin was boiled with 28% sulphuric acid under reflux for 3-4 hours but the methoxyl value remained unchanged. The same sample was boiled under reflux with 2*N*-alcoholic KOH for the same period but the lignin had the same methoxyl content as before, *viz.*, 19.18%. This shows that all the methoxyl groups in jute-lignin are linked in the form of ether.

As the lignin after methylation was obtained in the form of a tarry mass which could not be purified without taking recourse to alkali boiling, it was not possible to detect any carboxyl group by methylation with dimethyl sulphate. The fully methylated product had practically the same methoxyl value even when it was boiled with 28% sulphuric acid or alcoholic caustic potash under reflux for 3-4 hours.

Methylated jute-lignin was oxidised with 5*N*-nitric acid following the procedure of Phillips and Goss (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3466) but no anisic acid could be detected in the oxidation products.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methylation of lignin.—About 2 g. of very finely powdered lignin were intimately mixed with 25 c.c. of 45% KOH in a Nessler's tube fitted with a rubber cork, through which passed a mechanical stirrer and a separating funnel. Dimethyl sulphate (30 c.c.) was slowly added drop by drop within 3-4 hours to the solution maintained at $20\text{--}22^\circ$ and stirred all the while. Next day the pasty mass obtained

by decanting the liquid, was boiled with dilute caustic soda to decompose the excess of dimethyl sulphate, washed thoroughly with water and dried at 105°. Methoxyl value was determined according to Zeisel's method. The same process of methylation was repeated three to four times until the methoxyl value was constant. The results are shown in Table I. It is worth mentioning here that at higher temperatures the methoxyl value rose up more slowly, thus at 60°, after successive methylations for 5 times, the methoxyl content was only 28·65%, while it required only 3 such treatments to reach the maximum figure at 20°. Further, it was found necessary to add 3 times the KOH Urban used in order to facilitate stirring. Before each fresh treatment with dimethyl sulphate it was essential to have the lignin in the pulverised form and mixed thoroughly with the caustic potash, otherwise the process had to be repeated a larger number of times to effect maximum methylation.

TABLE I.

No. of treatment.	(a) Jute-lignin separated at room temperature.		(b) Jute-lignin isolated by the modified method.		(c) Sample (b) boiled with 28% H ₂ SO ₄ .	
	OMe.	Temp. of 1st appearance of MeI.	OMe.	Temp. of 1st appearance of MeI.	OMe.	Temp. of 1st appearance of MeI.
	16·41%	92°-93°	19·18%	92°-93°	19·05%	92°-63°
1	20·87	...	28·34	84°-85°	26·87	84°-85°
2	24·85	84°-85°	33·56	„	32·45	„
3	32·54	„	34·51	„	36·70	„
4	35·87	„	34·32	„	36·62	„
5	35·68	„

Samples (a) and (c) reduced Fehling's solution before methylation but not after. Sample (c) was dark coloured and fairly soluble in dilute caustic alkalis before treatment with dimethyl sulphate but the colour became light brown on methylation and also it was quite insoluble in alkali afterwards. All the methylated products were practically insoluble in the usual solvents. None melted within 300°.

Formaldehyde was estimated in the final product of sample (b) by the dimedone method (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 691) and the figure after solubility correction was 2·36% which shows that the dioxymethylene group was unaffected during methylation.

TABLE II.

Genuine lignin from jute.		Genuine jute-lignin.		Methylated lignin of sample (b).	
Treatment.	OMe.	Treatment.	OMe.	Treatment.	OMe.
—	19.18%	—	34.51%
Boiled with 28% H ₂ SO ₄	18.78	Boiled with 2N- alcoholic KOH for 3-4 hrs.	19%	Boiled with 28% H ₂ SO ₄	34.24
				Boiled with alco- holic KOH	34.15

Oxidation of jute-lignin after methylation.—5 G. of the fully methylated lignin (with 34.51% methoxyl) and 50 c.c. of 5N-nitric acid were heated on a water-bath for 1/2 hour, cooled, filtered and washed. The ethereal extract of the filtrate on evaporation gave a syrupy liquid mixed with nitric acid. The small quantity of solid separated therefrom after the removal of nitric acid was found to be oxalic acid (m.p. 101°).

SUMMARY.

1. By methylating jute-lignin, it has been shown that it contains 5 OH groups in a molecular weight of 830.
2. As the reducing lignin no longer reduces Fehling's solution after methylation, it is concluded that jute-lignin contains no aldehyde group.
3. From the temperature at which CH₃I first appears, it is inferred that OCH₃ is linked to benzene ring in natural lignin.
4. All methoxyl groups in jute-lignin are of ether type, as also those entering the molecule on methylation.
5. By the oxidation of methylated jute-lignin no anisic acid could be detected.
6. No information regarding the carboxyl group was obtained from the methylation of lignin as alkali boiling could not be avoided during purification.

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